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Resume. The main risk factor for complications in percutaneous echinococcectomy is non-compliance with the intervention methodology, the use of the Seldinger method and the use of ineffective intraoperative germicides.

Key words: relapse, echinococcosis, liver, cysts.

The history of surgical treatment of echinococcosis goes back thousands of years. Hippocrates also tried to empty the echinococcal cyst by cauterizing the abdominal wall above the cyst with the calenic gland [2,4,6,8,10,12,40]. In 1871 Lindermann published data on the first simultaneous marsupialization of the echinococcal cyst. The first two-moment echinococcectomy was performed in 1876. Volkmann. The disadvantage of these methods was the long existence of an open cavity. Trying to reduce the number of postoperative complications, Thronton performed a deaf suturing of the fibrous capsule with the anterior abdominal wall in 1883 g. In 1890 To prevent purulent complications, T. Billroth introduced 10% iodoform-glycerol emulsion into the emptying echinococcal cyst cavity, but caused poisoning of the patient [2,29,31,33,35]. Among domestic scientists, such surgeons as A.A. Bobrov, S.P. Spasokukotsky 21 N.I. Napalkov, V.M. Mysh, R.P. Askerkhanov made a great contribution to the development of liver echinococcosis surgery in 1894 [1,6,8,10,12,34]. For the first time in Russia, A.A. Bobrov performed a closed echinococcectomy with treatment of the residual cavity with physiological solution. For disinfection of the cyst cavity, Spasokukotsky S.P. proposed a 2% solution of formalin. Pericystectomy was first performed in 1888. Lawson - Tain. In our country, this operation since 1904 Napalkov N.I. began to use. The most radical operation in liver echinococcosis is liver resection with echinococcal cyst without opening the latter. This operation was first performed in 1888. Loretta.

In Russia, this operation was first performed by Mysh V.I. in 1912 [18, 27, 29]. The French surgeon P. Delbet proposed in 1896 to complete the operation by blind suturing the cavity of the fibrous capsule, which, however, led to significant complications associated with damage to the blood and bile vessels during stitching [1,2]. Many different classifications of hepatic echinococcosis surgery have now been proposed. In 1976 O.B. Milonov developed his classification of surgical methods for the treatment of echinococcosis

[1,3,5,7,9,11,24]. 1. Closed echinococectomy - without opening its membranes: a) ideal echinococectomy - cyst removal along with fibrous capsule b) resection or removal of an organ with an unopened cyst 2. Open echinococectomy - removal of the parasitic cyst after dissection of their membranes. Askerkhanov R.P. in his classification distinguished three main methods of surgical treatment [26,28,30,32,34]: 1. removal of only echinococcal cyst elements without fibrous sheath (echinococectomy); 2. removal of the parasite along with the fibrous capsule (pericystectomy); 3. removal of echinococcal cyst by organ resection. Within each of the methods, it is also distinguished: a) the ideal echinococectomy - removal of the bubble without opening the chitin shell or after opening it; b) closed echinococectomy - suturing of the cavity of the fibrous capsule without drainage; c) semi-closed echinococectomy - leaving drainage in the residual cavity after its capitalization; d) omentoplasty - plugging the cavity of the fibrous capsule with a strand of a large omentum; e) open echinococectomy - suturing the edges of the fibrous capsule cavity to the wound of the anterior abdominal wall with plugging of the cyst cavity with ointment swabs and/or a thick drainage tube.

To date, the issue of classification of surgical interventions in echinococcosis is of considerable disagreement. This is due to the fact that, despite the fact that a number of authors indicate a commonality of opinions regarding the terms "open echinococectomy" and "closed echinococectomy," this does not correspond to reality [1]. The fact is that some of the authors understand closed echinococectomy as an operation in which the echinococcal cyst is removed without opening its cavity, which excludes contact of healthy tissues with the germinal elements of the parasite [13,15,17], while other authors define the terms "open echinococectomy" and "closed echinococectomy" in relation to the residual cavity (blind suturing or suturing of the edges of the fibrous capsule to the wound of the anterior abdominal wall) [19,21,23].

Another stumbling block regarding the treatment of echinococcosis is the choice of germicide. At various times, various solutions have been used as germicide, such as ether, formalin, hydrogen peroxide solution, alcohol and table salt solution in various concentrations, chlorine compounds, vaseline oil, etc. Experience with these drugs revealed a number of disadvantages associated with insufficient germicidal activity and toxicity [14,16,18,20,22,25,27]. 80-100% aqueous glycerol solution and 30% sodium chloride solution have proven germicidal activity on protoskolexes and acephalocysts. However, the disadvantage of the sodium chloride solution is its "self-dilution" and the

associated loss of antiparasitic properties [1]. Nevertheless, despite the proven antiparasitic efficacy of glycerol and many years of experience in the unsuccessful use of other germicidal substances, the literature, including foreign ones, still contains data on the use of ineffective drugs listed above [15, 19, 20]. Since the end of the last century, effective germicides have been introduced into clinical practice, and therefore the methods of treatment of echinococcosis are now divided into conservative and surgical. In turn, surgical methods are divided into traditional and miniinvasive (puncture and video endoscopic). Currently, chemotherapy with albendazole is used as a conservative method of treatment [1, 2].

Methods of surgical treatment are constantly improving, showing rather successful results. Despite this, scientists do not abandon attempts to find a way to medicate echinococcosis, which could allow them to refuse surgical treatment [4, 7]. In recent years, many publications have appeared on the successful conservative therapy of echinococcosis, so the question of choosing between conservative treatment and surgery remains relevant [1]. Most authors believe that chemotherapy cannot be an alternative to the surgical method and recommend its use only in combination with it or in those forced cases when surgery cannot guarantee a complete cure for echinococcosis [2,12]. In traditional operative treatments, surgeons, depending on the localization of the echinococcal cyst, use various surgical accesses. These are access to Fedorov and Kocher, and middle access, and access of the Mercedes type [1,2]. To date, the most common open methods of surgery in liver echinococcosis are echinococcectomy, ideal echinococcectomy, pericystectomy, liver resection [5,7,9]. The most effective volume of surgery for echinococcal liver damage is also a subject of debate among scientists to this day. The basis of disagreement is the attitude towards the fibrous capsule. There is still no consensus on whether a fibrous capsule can carry germinal elements and cause disease recurrence [1]. This necessitates a thorough analysis of the literature, assessment of the causes of complications and relapses and the development of an algorithm for percutaneous interventions in liver echinococcosis, which served as the basis for the present study.

Purpose of the study. Improvement of treatment results in patients with hepatic echinococcosis due to development of algorithm for prevention and treatment of complications in percutaneous echinococcectomy.

Study material and methods: For the purpose of the study, 112 inpatient charts of patients who underwent miniinvasive interventions for liver echinococcosis

were analyzed in the clinic of faculty and hospital surgery of the Abu Ali Ibn Sin Bukhara Medical Institute. The almost twofold predominance of women over men in the structure of the incidence of echinococcus is associated with their greater involvement in the cooking process, participation in the production of skins, housekeeping, with the care of cattle, etc.

All patients had complete blood and urine count, biochemical blood count and coagulogram. Liver function was assessed by total protein and fractions, direct and indirect bilirubin, aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), gamma-glutamine transferase, blood glucose, serum amylase, creatinine and urea. Activated partial thromboplastin time, fibrinogen concentration in blood, international normalized ratio, prothrombin index were determined to assess the condition of the blood coagulation system.

Ultrasound was performed as the primary diagnostic method for echinococcosis for all patients. A high-end ultrasonic scanner Hitachi Aloka ProSound Alpha 6 Premier (Japan) was used. The examination was performed in the patient's supine position and on the left side in the morning on an empty stomach. Right and left lobes and liver gates were examined. The study evaluated the size, shape, contours, echogenicity, echostructure, vascular architectonics of the liver. Next, the localization, shape, contours, size and number of cysts in the liver, their relationship with the portal, lower hollow veins, bile ducts and other surrounding structures were evaluated. Ultrasound was performed on all patients when they went to the clinic. In the postoperative period, ultrasound was performed every 4 days to assess changes in the cysts.

Percutaneous puncture and antiparasitic treatment of echinococcal cysts. Literature data indicate the admissibility of antiparasitic treatment of small-sized echinococcal cysts followed by anti-relapse chemotherapy. The validity of puncture of these cysts is a decrease in the duration and duration of subsequent anti-relapse therapy. In this regard, we consider it inappropriate to complicate the operation. Therefore, with cysts less than 3 centimeters in diameter, we performed only puncture and antiparasitic treatment of these cysts without drainage and removal of the chitin shell. Cysts of 3 or less centimeters in diameter were detected in 71 patients.

The preparatory stages of the operation were performed in the same way as in the previous method. However, to perform this operation, we did not use a needle-catheter complex, but a Chiba needle with a diameter of 20-22G. Under UZ control, the latter, in compliance with all the above safety principles, was

introduced into the cyst cavity. The stylet was then removed, a syringe was attached to the needle, and the contents were aspirated. Then, 87% aqueous glycerol solution was introduced into the cyst cavity with exposure of 8-10 minutes. When using this technique, it is especially important to fix the needle firmly and prevent its reavailable movements, since in this case there is a risk not only of the needle coming out of the cyst, but also of damaging the opposite wall. Therefore, the entire operation must be performed under constant CD control. After exposure, glycerol was re-aspirated and the needle was removed. The operation was completed and the patient was transferred to the ward.

Conclusions: 1. The main risk factor for complications in percutaneous echinococectomy is non-compliance with the intervention methodology, the use of the Seldinger method and the use of ineffective intraoperative germicides. 2. Intraoperative complications increase significantly with reciprocal movements of the instrument in the cyst until its complete disinfection and with the use of ineffective germicides.

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